

METHODS OF PROFESSIONAL SELF-DEVELOPMENT OF A PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHER

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Abstract. *One of the methods that significantly affects the increase in the pedagogical skills of the teacher, his qualifications, pedagogical abilities, pedagogical competence is constant self-development and improvement of his qualifications. This article talks about how it is possible to form this competence in future primary school teachers.*

Keywords: *competence, professional competence, method, qualification, activity criteria.*

МЕТОДЫ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОГО САМОРАЗВИТИЯ УЧИТЕЛЯ НАЧАЛЬНЫХ КЛАССОВ

Аннотация. *Одним из методов, существенно влияющих на повышение педагогического мастерства педагога, его квалификации, педагогических способностей, педагогической компетентности, является постоянное саморазвитие и повышение его квалификации. В данной статье рассказывается о том, как можно сформировать данную компетенцию у будущих учителей начальных классов.*

Ключевые слова: *компетентность, профессиональная компетентность, метод, квалификация, критерии деятельности.*

The future primary school teacher, first of all, must be well mastered and educated in the content, goals and objectives of organizing the educational process himself. Because the educational process is a complex process, it will be necessary to give education to students along with education. Without upbringing, the teacher can't give the absent upbringing to the student, and some disagreements and problems arise in the classroom.

It is necessary for the future primary school teacher to be able to analyze the composition of the organization of the educational process, the content of the main innovative reforms, to form the interaction and connection of the subject of the specialty with other disciplines, to be able to use informative information, to be able to perfectly know the tasks of

Jean Piaget of modern pedagogy today described the goal of the educational process as "The goal of Education is to educate creative, inventive people who are able to create new products, and not be content with repeating what previous generations have created."

Every pedagogue is engaged in creativity, it must be said that innovating is creativity. Pedagogical activity is a continuous creative process, and a creative thinking pedagogue creates the most effective pedagogical system in certain conditions.

Currently, the most important process in the assimilation of modern pedagogical knowledge is acquired knowledge in youth. After all, it was not for nothing that our ancestors said that "the knowledge gained in youth is like a pattern carved into a stone." It is considered very important that he regularly repeats the knowledge gained, works more on himself and, in the future, has more knowledge in the subjects he teaches, being able to interest students in reading.

No development will come if you do not know in advance about all the subtleties and unique features of your own personality. Self-knowledge is the most important source for the study of personality. Only the person himself is able to form the most accurate picture of himself, based on his experience, life choices and actions.

Without it, it is difficult to develop in absolutely any field, including professional, and all because each person has his own personal abilities that distinguish him from other people. If we were all the same, like people from a copier, then we would hardly be able to achieve success in any business. After all, then it would have quite strongly distinguished us from the rest of the inhabitants of the planet. "If a person seeks to do what he is doing correctly and more efficiently, the work process he is doing will become a process of creativity" (John Apdike).

In fact, the work will be more efficient only if all the goals and aspirations are focused on the work being done. We will be able to see the approach of some young educators who work day and night tirelessly on themselves, who are in motion to become a mature specialist in their profession, to work without looking at the educational process.

The development of abilities in a person is largely determined by three factors:

- presence of predisposition to certain activities;
- the need to engage in certain activities, the presence of interest;
- social factor.

Such abilities are manifested in any type of activity. Scientific, artistic process, production, market economy, including in pedagogical activity.

In pedagogical activity, the future primary school teacher will have to regularly read more books and improve his knowledge, work mentally in order to develop creative abilities. The activities of a teacher who does not know how to use current modern technologies do not go far. Why say, the XXI work became the age of "development of modern technologies", and we see that the level of students coming to school, the indicator of mastering, is also much higher than before.

In general, creative abilities are formed, such as being able to see a problem, develop a hypothesis and come up with ways to verify it, collect and analyze data, draw conclusions and see the possibilities of applying results, and be able to see the stages of solving the problem.

The levels of development of creative abilities are divided into high, medium, low levels.

A high level is a person's desire for knowledge, the uniqueness of his thinking, the richness of his imagination, the ability to create new ideas, an easy and quick transition to a new type of activity. Such people achieve high success in creativity, take prizes in various competitions.

Intermediate level-a person feels the need to enrich his knowledge, but cannot independently perform tasks, come up with interesting ideas, but cannot correctly evaluate them, perform them. Participates in competitions.

Low level-a person does not demonstrate a desire for creativity, his thinking is not flexible, his imagination is not developed, he does not try to present the results of activity.

An important condition for pedagogical creativity is that the teacher has a love for his profession, in which there is a desire for professional growth, development.

A creative pedagogue is able to deeply analyze the situation that has arisen, understand its essence, create a positive solution, conduct a fantastic experiment and apply it in practice. Able to create a new idea, relying on pedagogical and psychological knowledge.

The creative potential of any educator is determined by such characteristics as the qualities of a creative person. Such characteristics can be recognized as the characteristics of a creative educator to be able to see alternative paths, to be critical of thoughts, to deviate from superficial conclusions, to be able to understand the problem in depth, to think promising, not to follow pedagogical ideas that have become traditional and are recognized by many specialists, to innovate and apply without fear of difficulties.

Other scientists have listed such qualities as the ability to quickly and easily embody thoughts as signs of a creative person, be able to create images and new combinations of them in the imagination, evaluate and critically think about evidence, information, have sorted knowledge of the work, compact information, generalize it, allocate non-essential ones.

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